

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF CERAMIC FACED ARMOURS BACKED BY COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the design and testing of a ceramic faced armour backed by a composite plate is presented. This armour was backed by an additional fibrous armour separated from the former by an air chamber. In the experiments, 7.62 NATO projectiles were fired against targets having different areal densities. Ceramic facings of AD 96 alumina and a mixture of boron nitride and silicon nitride were tested, while the composites considered were either aramid fibers embedded in a vinylester matrix, high tenacity aramid fibers embedded in a vinylester matrix or polyethylene fibers embedded in a polyethylene matrix. Impact velocities ranging from 816 m/s to 951 m/s were considered.

Keywords: aramid, polyethylene, ceramics, armour design, ballistic impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

The high strength and low density of fabrics, makes it a very attractive material for the design of lightweight armours, such as those employed for body armours, helmets, or protection in structures such as helicopters, tanks and aircrafts. Thus, a large effort has been directed to the research of the behaviour of either laminated fabrics [1] or woven fabrics [2-5] under impact loading. Due to its erosive properties, high compressive strength and low density, ceramic materials have also found large applicability in armour design, as a means of causing projectile destruction and spreading of the impact load on a larger area of the target. Consequently, ceramic faced armours backed by composite plates are frequently employed in lightweight armour design.

In this work, ceramic faced armours backed by composite plates were designed in such a manner that an armour arrangement composed by the aforementioned armour and a second fibrous armour would be able to defeat the 7.62 NATO projectile, within allowable values of the maximum armour deflection. The design criterion was based on the idea that the ceramic plate simply distributes the impact load on a larger area than that of the impact, whereas the composite plate absorbs all the energy of the impact. The backup plates considered were either polyethylene fabric in a polyethylene matrix, aramid fabric in a vinylester matrix or high tenacity aramid fabric in a vinylester matrix, while the ceramic facing was either alumina or a mixture of boron nitride (BN) and silicon nitride (Si_3N_4). The second fibrous armour included in the arrangement had been previously designed to arrest both the Magnum .357 and the 9 mm Parabellum threats, and it was made of high tenacity aramid fabrics. The result of the impact experiments show that the design criterion employed allows us to make a rather conservative design of the armours, thus being a very useful tool in lightweight armour design.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Armour design procedure.

The model employed for the design of the ceramic/composite armour assumes that when a projectile impacts a ceramic faced armour at an impact velocity v larger than the ballistic limit v_1 , then the residual kinetic energy of the projectile after perforation can be estimated as $m_p(v-v_1)^2/2$, where m_p is the projectile mass [6]. In this way, the above armour was designed for perforation, but after reducing the initial kinetic energy of the projectile, which was a 7.62 NATO projectile, to a value comparable to that corresponding to the impact energy of the .357 Magnum and 9 mm Parabellum projectiles. This latter value is known to be about 670 J, which was employed as a design reference. The above criterion lays on the fact that after perforation of the first armour, the projectile attacks the fibrous armour, which is separated from the previous one by an air chamber 7 mm thick, and that it is known to be able to defeat by itself both the .357 Magnum and the 9 mm Parabellum projectiles. Figure 1 shows an aspect of the three aforementioned projectiles.

An expression for the ballistic limit v_1 of a ceramic/backing plate package, which has been proved to be valid for composite backing plates [6], has been proposed by Florence [7]. This model is based on the idea that the ceramic tile spreads the load from the impact over a zone of radius R , and gives an explicit expression for v_1 as:

$$v_1 = (\sigma_0 \epsilon h_c \pi R^2 (1 + \psi) / 0.91 m_p)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

In this expression, σ_0 is the ultimate tensile strength of the backing plate, ϵ is the rupture strain of the backing plate, h_c the thickness of the ceramic, m_p the projectile mass as before, ψ the ratio m_t/m_p , m_t being the mass of the target involved in the penetration process and, as previously mentioned, R is the radius of the zone of the target affected by the impact. R is evaluated as $R=r+2h_c$, r being the projectile radius, and m_t is computed as $m_t=\pi R^2(\rho_c h_c + \rho_b h_b)$, ρ_c and ρ_b being the mass densities of the ceramic and the backup plate respectively, and h_b the thickness of the backup plate.

In order to test the reliability of the design criterion, in addition to the baseline design (which was performed for a residual kinetic energy value of 670 J), additional armour packages with a backing plate having more or fewer layers than the baseline design were also considered. The values used in the computations were the following. The projectile radius was $r=3.6$ mm and its mass was $m_p=9.55$ g. For the aramid/vinylester composite, a density of 1270 kgm^{-3} , a rupture strain of 3.3% and an ultimate tensile strength of 2.95 GPa were used. For the high tenacity aramid/vinylester composite, a mass density of 1240 kgm^{-3} , a rupture strain of 3.3% and an ultimate tensile strength of 3.38 GPa were considered, while for the polyethylene/polyethylene composite a density of 887 kgm^{-3} , a rupture strain of 3.5% and an ultimate tensile strength of 3.1 GPa were used. The alumina density was $\rho_a=3700$ kgm^{-3} , and for $\text{BN}+\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ the density was $\rho_b=2680$ kgm^{-3} . The ceramic tile was 6 mm AD 96, 5mm AD96 or 5 mm $\text{BN}+\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$, alternatively.

2.2 Impact experiments.

Mixed armours, composed by the designed armour and the fibrous armour, separated the former from the latter by an air chamber 7 mm thick, were then built and subjected to the impact of 7.62 NATO projectiles at velocities ranging from 816 m/s to 951 m/s. In total, 34 impact tests were made. In Table 1 the description of each of the tested armours, its corresponding total areal densities and the impact velocity can be found. In the last column of Table 1 the theoretical residual kinetic energy of the projectile after hypothetical perforation of the ceramic/composite armour is also shown. The cases of partial or complete perforation are also indicated in such a Table. We can appreciate from Table 1 that complete perforation of the armour package resulted only in three cases, having theoretical residual kinetic energies after perforation of the first armour of at least 989 J, well above the design value of 670 J. Furthermore, it is observed that the perforation of the first armour

took place only in 12 cases (including the tree cases when complete perforation was also observed), in spite of the fact that the baseline design was made for perforation of the first armour. A limit situation of projectile detention after rupture of the last layer of the backing plate of the ceramic/composite armour was observed in 10 cases, and in the 12 remaining cases projectile arrest took place even without complete rupture of the first armour.

Figure 2 shows an aspect of the impacted side of an alumina AD-96 target backed by the aramid/vinylester composite after impact. Figures 3 (a) and 3 (b) show the front and rear views of a perforated polyethylene/polyethylene backing plate after an experiment, and Figure 4 shows the rear view of a perforated aramid/vinylester composite plate. Figure 5 shows a view of the projectile before and after the impact. As it can be appreciated from this latter Figure, the recovered part of the projectile after the impact consists of an aggregate of metallic fragments which may or may not contain some ceramic fragments, and that it disintegrates very easily on hand contact. Figures 6 (a) to (c) show views of some polyethylene plates after the impact, which have been cut through planes intersecting the impact crater. Cases when either projectile arrest by the composite armour, projectile arrest by the fibrous armour or complete perforation took place are included in such a Figure. Similar views for the case of aramid/vinylester plates are shown in Figure 7. Delamination was found to have a limited extent for polyethylene plates, while it was found to be very extended for the aramid/vinylester plates.

In Figure 8 the maximum deflection of the fibrous armour along the axis of impact, commonly referred to as trauma, is plotted as a function of the total areal density of the ceramic/composite armour, including the fibrous armour, in the case of an aramid/vinylester backing plate. Figures 9 and 10 depict the graphical representation of the same variables for the case of high tenacity aramid/vinylester and polyethylene/polyethylene backup plates, respectively. We appreciate from such figures that, for a given areal density, BN+Si₃N₄ ceramic tiles tend to give smaller trauma values than the AD 96 alumina tiles. Thus, the above figures suggest that BN+Si₃N₄ ceramic facings are more efficient than AD 96 alumina tiles, making easier the absorption by the target of the energy of the impact.

3. DISCUSSION

Delamination in composites is a problem which has been studied by several authors [8-10], and which is frequently associated to the propagation of a crack-like imperfection along an interface. In the impact experiments performed, delamination was found to be very important in the aramid/vinylester plates, frequently involving delamination along many interfaces and being very extended along the radial coordinate. Delamination was found to be more limited for polyethylene/polyethylene plates, where often only a single delamination plane was observed. In some cases, several delamination planes were detected in polyethylene/polyethylene plates, but anyway the radial extent of delamination was of the order of the crater diameter. In general, the extent of delamination was observed to be mainly affected by the composite plate thickness, increasing as the composite plate thickness increased. Thus, it can be proposed that the delamination in the composites tested is mainly due to shear stresses that develop at the interfaces due to the plate deflection caused by the impact, and that increase as the plate stiffness increases.

Since it is expected that interaction between the ceramic/composite armour and the fibrous armour had taken place during impact, it is naturally concluded that at a given instant both armours, and not only the first impacted armour as assumed in design, will contribute to projectile arrest. This fact may naturally provide a safety margin for armour design, making possible projectile arrest in conditions much more unfavourable than those of design. Consequently, it is not surprising that perforation of the first armour (which was a design condition), had been observed in only 12 cases from the 34 impact tests performed.

As it can be verified in Figures 3 and 4, textile dynamics plays a role in the penetration of composite plates. This fact becomes clear from the squareness of the penetration imprint which is observed in the above Figures. This causes a departure from the assumption that the zone affected by the impact is circular. Thus, a modification of the model to take into account of this effect seems in order. This may be accomplished by introducing a shape factor in equation (1), modifying the value of the radius R of the zone affected by the impact, but it is not expected that this effect has an important influence in the model predictions.

The main parameters characterizing the ceramic resistance to penetration have been not fully identified up to now. Nevertheless, there is an obvious need to include, even in an approximate manner, the influence of ceramic behaviour in the model predictions of the armour response. In fact, this work has shown that BN+Si₃N₄ ceramic is more efficient than AD 96 alumina, even under the same design conditions. Thus, the role of the ceramic tile is not fully described by the assumption of load distribution within an area defined by the cone of fractured ceramics, and additional research in this respect should be made.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a criterion for the design of ceramic/composite armours has been applied to the design of a lightweight armour for defeating the 7.62 NATO projectile. The above criterion is based on the idea that the ceramic tile simply spreads the impact load on a larger area than that of the impact, whereas the composite plate absorbs all the energy from the impact. The ballistic experiments performed with the designed armours made evident a very good ballistic performance of the armours, which exhibited a rather conservative behaviour with respect to that assumed in design. Thus, the design criterion employed in this work has shown to be a very efficient tool in lightweight armour design.

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Table 1. Areal density, impact velocity and theoretical residual kinetic energy after hypothetical perforation of the ceramic/composite armour, for each of the armours tested.

Armour	Areal Density (kg/m ²)	Impact Velocity (m/s)	Theoretical Residual Kinetic Energy (J)
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 6mm	35.100	827.03	837.10 *
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 6mm	36.180	815.70	658.00
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 6mm	37.850	821.09	503.50
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 5mm	35.300	818.75	822.50
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 5mm	35.300	831.47	873.70
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 5mm	36.900	833.26	735.50
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 5mm	36.900	831.75	730.00
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 5mm	39.700	833.82	530.60
Aramid/vinylester + AD96 5mm	39.700	823.78	499.00
Aramid/vinylester + BN+Si ₃ N ₄ 5mm	32.960	872.89	897.00 *
Aramid/vinylester + BN+Si ₃ N ₄ 5mm	35.750	857.12	691.10
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 6mm	34.200	819.35	804.80 *
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 6mm	35.300	839.73	729.40 *
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 6mm	35.300	950.67	1202.30 **
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 6mm	36.440	823.44	539.50
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 5mm	34.310	833.54	870.40
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 5mm	34.100	845.02	917.80
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 5mm	35.800	835.83	720.80
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 5mm	35.800	826.69	687.30
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 5mm	38.030	821.43	493.30
Aramid Ht/vinylester + AD96 5mm	38.030	833.20	530.10
Aramid Ht/vinylester + BN+Si ₃ N ₄ 5mm	31.300	872.89	915.80 *
Aramid Ht/vinylester + BN+Si ₃ N ₄ 5mm	33.800	857.12	639.00 *
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 6mm	32.350	824.39	888.30 *
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 6mm	33.300	820.02	705.60 *
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 6mm	34.210	831.13	603.50
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 5mm	31.420	822.77	886.00
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 5mm	31.420	945.04	1460.34 **
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 5mm	33.300	830.87	701.00
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 5mm	33.300	828.73	693.60
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 5mm	35.100	824.12	500.40
Polyethylene/polyethylene + AD96 5mm	35.100	828.60	514.30
Polyethylene/polyethylene + BN+Si ₃ N ₄ 5mm	26.630	840.72	989.00 **
Polyethylene/polyethylene + BN+Si ₃ N ₄ 5mm	28.700	834.58	757.00 *

* Perforation of the first armour.

** Complete perforation.

Figure 1. A side view of the 7.62 NATO (left), the Magnum .357 (middle) and the 9mm Parabellum (right) projectiles.

Figure 2. Front view of an AD 96 alumina faced and aramid/vinylester backed target after impact.

Figure 3. A perforated polyethylene/polyethylene plate after the experiment: front view (left) and rear view (right).

Figure 4. Rear view of a perforated aramid/vinylester plate after the impact.

Figure 5. A view of the projectile before (right) and after (left) the impact.

Figure 6. A view of polyethylene/polyethylene plates after the impact, after cutting through planes intersecting the impact crater: projectile arrested by the composite plate (top); projectile arrested by the fibrous armour (middle); complete perforation (bottom). The arrow indicates the impact direction.

Figure 7. A view of aramid/vinylester plates after the impact, after cutting through planes intersecting the impact crater: projectile arrested by the composite plate (top); projectile arrested by the fibrous armour (middle); complete perforation (bottom). The arrow indicates the impact direction.

Figure 8. Trauma (maximum deflection of the fibrous armour along the axis of the impact) as a function of the total areal density for armours with aramid/vinylester backings. The shaded area corresponds to the zone where the experimental data for the alumina facings falls.

Figure 9. Trauma (maximum deflection of the fibrous armour along the axis of the impact) as a function of the total areal density for armours with high tenacity aramid/vinylester backings. The shaded area corresponds to the zone where the experimental data for the alumina facings falls.

Figure 10. Trauma (maximum deflection of the fibrous armour along the axis of the impact) as a function of the total areal density for armours with polyethylene/polyethylene backings. The shaded area corresponds to the zone where the experimental data for the alumina facings falls.

